

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING METHODS IN THE SYSTEM OF EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11515528>

Abstract. Activities are the various ways in which these methods can be put into practice, whilst teaching methods are the more general strategies utilized to assist students in meeting learning objectives. Instructional strategies benefit pupils in the following way: -grasp the course material and learn how to use it in certain situations.

Teachers need to choose which instructional strategies will best serve a certain learning objective. This alignment is necessary for it to be effective. An instructor should take learning outcomes, student needs, and the learning environment into account while making the best decision.

Keywords: student-centric, collaborative learning, flipped classroom, VAK, spaced learning, differentiated instruction, dual coding, role-playing.

Annotatsiya. O`qitish metodlari o`quvchilarga ta`lim natijalariga erishishga yordam berish uchun qo`llaniladigan kengroq usullardir, faoliyat esa bu usullarni amalga oshirishning turli yo`llaridir. O`qitish metodlari talabalarga quyidagilarda yordam beradi: -kurs mazmunini egallash va muayyan kontekstda tarkibni qanday qo`llashni o`rganish. O`qituvchilar qaysi o`qitish metodlari ma`lum bir ta`lim natijasini to`g`ri qo`llab-quvvatlashini aniqlashlari kerak. Uning samaradorligi ushbu moslashuvga bog`liq. Eng to`g`ri tanlov qilish uchun o`qituvchi ta`lim natijalarini, talaba ehtiyojlarini va o`quv muhitini hisobga olishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan, hamkorlikda o'rganish, teskari sinf, VAK, intervalgacha ta'lim, tabaqalashtirilgan o'qitish, dual kodlash, rolli o'yin.

Аннотация. Деятельность- это различные способы применения этих методов на практике, тогда как методы обучения - это более общие стратегии, используемые для помощи учащимся в достижении целей обучения. Стратегии обучения приносят пользу учащимся следующим образом: -усвоить материал курса и научиться использовать его в определенных ситуациях. Учителю необходимо выбрать, какие стратегии обучения лучше всего послужат определенной цели обучения. Такое

согласование необходимо для того, чтобы оно было эффективным. При принятии наилучшего решения преподаватель должен учитывать результаты обучения, потребности учащихся и среду обучения.

Ключевые слова: учащийся, совместное обучение, перевернутый класс, ВАК, пространственное обучение, дифференцированное обучение, двойное кодирование, ролевая игра.

Introduction. A teaching method is a set of principles and methods used by teachers to enable student learning. These strategies are determined partly by the subject matter to be taught, partly by the relative expertise of the learners, and partly by constraints caused by the learning environment. [1] For a particular, the nature of the subject matter, and the type of learning it is supposed to bring about. [2]

Teaching is a science that has its origins and rules, and it can be observed, measured, evaluated, and then its skills trained on. Raising the teacher's efficiency using teaching methods leads to raising the efficiency of public education, including its research aspects. The educational preparation for the teacher would deepen the human aspects of the teaching process, and develop the relationship between the faculty member and the student. Moreover, the frequent change in human knowledge, in terms of quantity and quality, made it very difficult, as the teacher is familiar with all its details and developments. Therefore, it is no longer possible to consider the volume of knowledge provided to the student as a single and adequate educational goal, but rather to emphasize providing the student with the skill to learn new things continuously with his efforts. What is important is for the student to learn how to think in scientific, logical, independent, and critical ways distinctive to his personality. Therefore, many researchers were alerted to this situation. As for teaching methods, there is no embarrassment to the efforts and monotony in delivering lectures within the four walls of an increasing number of students. These methods are negative because they do not follow the field to refer to the sources and the library, and they do not encourage self-education and the adoption of creation and innovation. In addition to the fact that the teacher is limited to just dictating the student and reading the brief notes, that includes selecting the entire teaching position. It was mentioned that teaching is a mini-process of education linked to activities and instructions that facilitate the learning process. Therefore, teaching is an interactive process of relationships, the environment, and the response of the learner, in which he has a partial role, and it must be judged in the final analysis by its results, which is the learner's learning.

Teaching methods are the broader techniques used to help students achieve learning outcomes, while activities are the different ways of implementing these methods. Teaching methods help students:

- ✓ master the content of the course
- ✓ learn how to apply the content in particular contexts

Instructors should identify which teaching methods will properly support a particular learning outcome. Its effectiveness depends on this alignment. To make the most appropriate choice, an instructor should consider learning outcomes, student needs, and the learning environment.

Consider the following example:

- ✓ **Learning outcome:** Solve a complex math equation.
- ✓ **Learning environment:** An in-person, upper-level math course with 20 students.
- ✓ **Teaching method:** Guided instruction. First, the instructor facilitates learning by modeling and scaffolding. Students take time to ask questions and receive clarifications. Next, students practice applying these skills together and then independently. The instructor uses formative assessment to check for understanding.

This example demonstrates alignment of what the instructor wants students to do, and how they are supported in these tasks. If the instructor chooses a different teaching method, such as a traditional lecture, students would need to process the lecture's content and apply principles simultaneously. This is very difficult to do and would lead to less successful outcomes.

Choosing the appropriate teaching method brings instruction to life while encouraging students to actively engage with content and develop their knowledge and skills.

The approaches for teaching can be broadly classified into teacher-centered and student-centered, although in practice teachers will often adapt instruction by moving back and forth between these methodologies depending on the learner's prior knowledge, learner expertise, and the desired learning objectives. [3] In the Student-Centered Approach to Learning, while teachers are the authority figure in this model, teachers and students play an equally active role in the learning process. This approach is also called authoritative. [4] The teacher's primary role is to coach and facilitate student learning and overall comprehension of material. Student learning is measured through both formal and informal forms of assessment, including group projects, student portfolios,

and class participation. Teaching and assessments are connected; student learning is continuously measured during teacher instruction. [5]

Types of teaching methods.

1. Student-Centric Discussion

A teaching technique known as “student-centric discussion” enables pupils to learn more about subjects or ideas through cooperation and teamwork. It entails in-depth conversations on subjects or concepts that eventually increase pupils’ self-assurance, output, and ability to put ideas into practice. Additionally, it enhances their speaking, listening, and comprehension abilities, which are reflected in their evaluations.

2. Collaborative Learning

The goal of the teaching method known as “collaborative learning” is to promote cooperation and partnership. It entails putting students with different skill levels in groups to solve problems or finish tasks. Diverse perspectives and ideas are produced by different minds, which aid in pupils’ better and more efficient understanding of the topics. There are significant connections between group dynamics and students’ learning outcomes, according to research on collaborative discussion and student learning. These findings have been applied in numerous instances to create targeted collaborative learning strategies, with positive outcomes for student learning.

3. Flipped Classroom

The revolutionary teaching method known as “flipped classroom” operates in opposition to conventional classroom instruction. In a conventional classroom, new ideas are taught to the students and they are expected to practice them on their own time. In contrast, students in a flipped classroom study new ideas at home and apply them in class through discussions, presentations, and lab exercises. Students become more engaged as a result, and it also strengthens their analytical and self-confidence.

4. VAK Teaching

The acronym for Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic education is VAK. This all-encompassing teaching approach emphasizes enhanced learning outcomes through the utilization of the three primary sensory receptors. Transitional beliefs state that kids often acquire and comprehend new ideas through their senses. Students can identify their dominant and preferred learning styles with the use of VAK instruction. For instance, visual learners can be satisfied by reading textbooks and taking notes, auditory learners can be satisfied by having

a topic taught to the class, and kinesthetic learners can be satisfied by practical assignments.

5. Spaced Learning

A teaching technique called spaced learning helps students practice a skill or retrieve information more effectively. One of the best instructional strategies a teacher may use in the classroom is this one. It entails segmenting a lengthy course into several manageable sessions or modules and ensuring that students comprehend them with the right breaks in between. Students are better able to retain material as a result. For instance, speaking English for ten minutes a day for ten days (a total of 100 minutes) is a more useful practice than speaking it continuously for one hundred minutes.

6. Dual Coding

Combining text and visuals, such as images, diagrams, and graphic organizers, with the subject matter is known as dual coding, and it helps students learn and retain information better. Even now, this is still one of the most effective teaching strategies. By using dual coding, you can provide kids with information that takes less mental work to understand by combining words and images. Using images to teach the life cycle of a butterfly: includes creating a pros and cons list with diagrams, creating a comic strip synopsis of a novel, or creating a timeline of a butterfly's life cycle with visual representation.

7. Differentiated Instruction

Do your pupils appear to be slipping behind? Do you wish to raise their level of performance? How do you adjust to the learning demands of students? This is when differentiated instruction as a teaching strategy enters the picture. The goal of differentiated instruction is to modify instruction to meet the needs of each unique learner. The success of this approach to instruction is ensured by the use of flexible grouping and constant evaluation, regardless of how teachers diversify their content, methods, products, or learning environment. Introducing audiobooks, for instance, might help students who struggle with studying through textbooks, or using artistic features to pique creative pupils' interest in non-artistic disciplines.

8. Problem-based Learning

The goal of problem-based learning (PBL), a student-centered method of instruction, is to solve real-world issues. Using this approach, students discover and analyze complicated problems in groups before coming up with answers through critical thinking and problem-solving techniques. PBL can be customized to fit each student's requirements and interests and be applied in a

range of academic subjects. PBL fosters the growth of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, which is one of its main benefits. Students are compelled to use their knowledge and abilities in a real-world situation when they work on real-world challenges, which can aid in their comprehension of the subject matter and foster a greater sense of respect for it.

9. Technology-based Learning

One kind of teaching approach that uses technology to enhance learning is called technology-based learning, or e-learning. This strategy can be used in a variety of ways, including multimedia presentations, online courses, and instructional software. For both students and teachers, technology-based learning can be flexible and easy, which is one of its key benefits. Students who are unable to attend traditional classroom-based courses or have hectic schedules can benefit greatly from the ability to access educational resources at any time and from any location via e-learning. Moreover, since students may go through the content at their speed and go over it again as needed, this method might offer a more customized learning experience. Technology-based learning also has the benefit of being participatory and interesting. Students can visualize difficult concepts and participate more dynamically with the subject by using multimedia resources like animations, interactive simulations, and films. Furthermore, by using online discussion forums to facilitate communication between students and teachers, this method can offer chances for collaborative learning.

10. Individual Learning

Self-directed learning, another name for individual learning, is a style of instruction where students are in charge of their education. By establishing their objectives, selecting their resources, and working at their speed, students are encouraged to participate actively in their education. Rather than controlling the learning process, the responsibility of the teacher is to offer direction, assistance, and resources. Customizing a learning experience to a student's interests and needs is one of the key benefits of individual learning. This has the potential to improve knowledge retention, motivation, and engagement. Furthermore, one-on-one instruction can support the growth of critical thinking, time management, and self-discipline, among other crucial abilities.

11. Expeditionary Learning

An approach to education called "expeditionary learning" emphasizes learning via investigation and experience. This method entails bringing students out of the classroom and into the real world where they will learn and grow

their abilities via practical projects and activities. This approach places a strong emphasis on getting students involved in their education and giving them chances to use what they have learned in relevant situations. The ability of expeditionary learning to foster a sense of community and teamwork among pupils is one of its key benefits. As students collaborate to solve problems and finish assignments, this approach promotes teamwork and communication. Additionally, it gives students the chance to grow as leaders and assume accountability for their own education. Expeditionary learning also encourages active and experience learning, which has the potential to be more memorable and interesting for students than typical classroom-based teaching. This approach contributes to the increased relevance and application of learning to students' daily lives by placing them in authentic scenarios.

12. Role-playing Method

One of the most popular forms of instruction is role-playing, in which students act out predetermined roles or scenarios to aid in their understanding of certain ideas or circumstances. This method works well in language arts, social studies, and science, among other subjects. Through first-hand experience and the exploration of many viewpoints, role-playing fosters empathy and critical thinking in pupils. Role-playing allows pupils to participate actively and engage, which is one of its key benefits. Students are more engaged in the learning process and are more likely to remember the material they are learning when they take on various roles. Students who struggle with traditional lecture-based learning or who find it difficult to stay interested in class may find this to be especially helpful. Another benefit of role-playing is that it gives children a chance to practice critical social and emotional abilities including empathy, communication, and problem-solving. Students can practice these abilities in a secure and encouraging setting by interacting with others in a role-playing scenario.

Teachers can better educate their students and motivate them to make positive changes in society by utilizing a variety of teaching techniques and ideas. Additionally, by using these instructional techniques and procedures, kids pick up new ideas and acquire vital life skills. If you are unsure about the best teaching techniques, you might want to enroll in courses like Learning Theories and Teaching Strategies, which will assist you in putting the best and most varied techniques into practice to raise student engagement and academic performance in general.

References:

1. "Teaching Methods". www.buffalo.edu. Retrieved 2024-03-13.

2. Westwood, P.(2008). What teachers need to know about Teaching methods. Camberwell, Vic, ACER Press.
3. Bockhove C, Campbell R (2020). "Chapter 8: "ADAPTING TEACHING" ". The EARLY CAREER FRAMEWORK HANDBOOK (PDF) (1 st ed.). Corwin Sage. pp. 76-79. ISBN 978-1-5297-2457-8.
4. Burger, C. , Strohmeier, D., Sprober , N., Bauman, S., Rigby, K (2015). "How teachers respond to school bullying: An examination of self-reported intervention strategy use, moderator effects, and concurrent use of multiple strategies". Teaching and Teacher Education. 51: 191-202. doi:10.1016/j.tate.2015.07.004. IISN 0742-051X.
5. "Teaching Methods". Teach.com. Retrieved 1 December 2017.

